

Strong Algebrability of Certain Subset of $C_0(X)$

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Abstract

In 2013, strong algebrability of $c_0 \setminus \cup_p \ell^p$ is proved by Bartoszewics and Glab. In this paper we expand this result to an arbitrary finite dimensional Banach space. The main theorem of this paper concerns that $C_0(X) \setminus \cup_p L^p(X)$ contains an infinitely generated free algebra, where X is a finite dimensional Banach space.

Keywords: Strong Algebrability; Pathological Properties; Free Algebra.

1. Introduction

Finding infinite dimensional algebraic structures and infinitely generated algebras in different subsets of various spaces is relatively new trend in mathematical analysis.

Recall that a subset S of a vector space V is called lineable if $S \cup \{0\}$ contains an infinite dimensional vector subspace of V . Also if V is a topological vector space then S is called spaceable if $S \cup \{0\}$ contains a closed infinite dimensional vector subspace of V . This notation was first appeared in an unpublished notes of Enflo and Gurariy. Aron and Gurariy was firstly published these notation in [2]. We should mention that Enflo's and Gurariy's unpublished notes were completed in collaboration with Seoane-Sepulveda and finally published in [8].

The term algebrability was introduced later in [3]: let κ is a cardinal number, if V is a linear algebra, S is said to be κ -algebrable if $S \cup \{0\}$ contains a κ -generated algebra, i.e. the minimal system of generators of this algebra has cardinality κ ([3]). Aron, Perez-Garcia and Seoane-Sepulveda approved in [4] that these to f non-convergent Fourier series is 1-algebrable. Aron and Seoane-Sepulveda established the algebrability of every where surjective functions on \mathbb{C} in [5], which was strengthened in [1]. Other algebrability results can be found in [10] and [11]. Here we will discuss some strengthening of the notion of algebrability.

Definition 1.1. Let κ is a cardinal number. We say that a subset S of an algebra A is strongly κ -algebrable if there exists a κ -generated free algebra B contained in $S \cup \{0\}$. In addition, if B is also dense in A , then A is called densely strongly κ -algebrable.

We call that, for a cardinal number κ , to say that an algebra A is a κ -generated free algebra, means that there exists a subset $Z = \{z_\alpha : \alpha < \kappa\} \subset A$ such that any function f from Z into some algebra A' can be uniquely extended to a homomorphism from A into A' . The set Z is called a set of free generators of the algebra A . If Z is a set of free generators of some subalgebra $B \subset A$, we say that Z is a set of free generators in the subalgebra A . If A is commutative, then a subset $Z = \{z_\alpha : \alpha < \kappa\} \subset A$ is a set of free generators in A if for each polynomial P and any $z_{\alpha_1}, \dots, z_{\alpha_n} \in Z$ we have

$$P(z_{\alpha_1}, \dots, z_{\alpha_n}) = 0 \text{ if and only if } P = 0.$$

The definition of strongly κ -algebrability was introduced in [9], though in several papers, sets which are shown to be algebrable are in fact strongly algebrable, and that is clear by the proofs (see [3] and [11]). Strong algebrability is in effect a stronger condition than algebrability: for example, C_0 is \aleph_0 -algebrable in C_0 but it is not strongly 1-algebrable (see [6]).

2. Strong Algebrability in $C_0(X)$

In 2013, Bartoszewicz and Głab have proved in [6] that $C_0 \setminus \bigcup_p \ell^p$ is densely strongly c -algebrable. The main theorem in this section extends this result to an arbitrary finite dimensional Banach space. Throughout this section, let X be a finite dimensional Banach space.

Theorem 2.1. The set $C_0(X) \setminus \bigcup_p L^p(X)$ is densely strongly c -algebrable in $C_0(X)$.

Proof. Let $\{r_\alpha : \alpha < \mathfrak{c}\}$ be a linearly independent subset of positive reals containing 1. Let A be the linear algebra generated by the set

$S = \{f_\alpha : X \rightarrow \mathbb{R}, \alpha < \mathfrak{c}\}$, where for each $\alpha < \mathfrak{c}$

$$f_\alpha = \frac{1}{\ln^{r_\alpha}(|x| + 2)}.$$

We will show that for each $\alpha < \mathfrak{c}$, $f_\alpha \in C_0(X)$, and also we will show that any non-trivial algebraic combination of elements of A is either a null function or is not in each $L^p(X)$, ($1 \leq p < \infty$).

First let $\varepsilon > 0$ is arbitrary. We have

$$\{x \in X : |f_\alpha(x)| \geq \varepsilon\} = \left\{x \in X : |x| + 2 \leq \exp\left(\frac{1}{\alpha^{r_\alpha}}\right)\right\}.$$

Since X is finite dimensional, so each closed disk in X is compact. So the above set is compact and therefore $f_\alpha \in C_0(X)$.

Now we want to prove that any non-trivial algebraic combination of elements of A is either a null function or is not in each $L^p(X)$, $(1 \leq p < \infty)$. To this end, let $\{k_i: 1 \leq i \leq n\}$ be a set of non-negative integers that are not simultaneously zero and $\beta_1, \dots, \beta_n \in \mathbb{R}$. We claim that $\sum_{i=1}^n \beta_i f_{\alpha_i}$ is not in each $L^p(X)$, $(1 \leq p < \infty)$. Without loss of generality let $\beta_1 \neq 0$ and $k_1 r_{\alpha_1} \leq k_2 r_{\alpha_2} \leq \dots \leq k_n r_{\alpha_n}$. Now we have

$$\left| \frac{\beta_1}{\ln^{k_1 r_{\alpha_1}}(|x| + 2)} + \frac{\beta_2}{\ln^{k_2 r_{\alpha_2}}(|x| + 2)} + \dots + \frac{\beta_n}{\ln^{k_n r_{\alpha_n}}(|x| + 2)} \right| \leq \frac{|\beta_1|}{\ln^{k_1 r_{\alpha_1}}(|x| + 2)} - \frac{|\beta_2|}{\ln^{k_2 r_{\alpha_2}}(|x| + 2)} - \dots - \frac{|\beta_n|}{\ln^{k_n r_{\alpha_n}}(|x| + 2)}.$$

Since $k_1 r_{\alpha_1}$ is smaller than each $k_2 r_{\alpha_2}, \dots, k_n r_{\alpha_n}$, there is $r > 0$ such that for all $x \in X$ with $|x| \geq r$ we have

$$\frac{|\beta_2|}{\ln^{k_2 r_{\alpha_2}}(|x| + 2)} + \dots + \frac{|\beta_n|}{\ln^{k_n r_{\alpha_n}}(|x| + 2)} < \frac{|\beta_1|}{\ln^{k_1 r_{\alpha_1}}(|x| + 2)}.$$

Hence for each $x \in X$ with $|x| \geq r$ we have

$$\left| \frac{\beta_1}{\ln^{k_1 r_{\alpha_1}}(|x| + 2)} + \frac{\beta_2}{\ln^{k_2 r_{\alpha_2}}(|x| + 2)} + \dots + \frac{\beta_n}{\ln^{k_n r_{\alpha_n}}(|x| + 2)} \right| \geq \frac{|\beta_1|}{2 \ln^{k_1 r_{\alpha_1}}(|x| + 2)}.$$

But $\frac{|\beta_1|}{2 \ln^q(|x| + 2)} \notin L^p(X)$, for all $p \geq 1$ and all $q > 0$. This shows that any algebraic combination of elements of A is either a null function or is not in each $L^p(X)$, $(1 \leq p < \infty)$.

Now, we claim that A is dense in $C_0(X)$. Consider the sub-algebra A_1 of $C(X)$ generated by two functions $f_1(x) = \frac{1}{\ln(|x| + 2)}$ and $f_2(x) = 1$. Let A_2 be a sub-algebra of A generated by the function f_1 . Note that

$$A_1 = \{f + a f_2: f \in A_2, a \in \mathbb{R}\}.$$

Let \tilde{X} be the one point compactification of X . Notice that $C(X)$ is isometrically isomorphic to $C(\tilde{X})$. Since A_1 separates the points of \tilde{X} and never vanishes on it, so by Stone-Weierstrass theorem, A_1 is uniformly dense in $C(X)$. Take a function $f \in C_0(X)$. There exists $g \in A_1$ with $\|f - g\| < \varepsilon/2$. Note that $|\lim_{|x| \rightarrow \infty} g(x)| \leq \varepsilon/2$. Put $\tilde{g} = g - \lim_{|x| \rightarrow \infty} g(x)$. Then $\|f - \tilde{g}\| < \varepsilon$. Now $\tilde{g} \in A_2 \subset A$. Thus A is dense in $C_0(X)$. This completes the proof. \square

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